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Synthesis of N-heterocycles containing 1,5-disubstituted-1H-tetrazole via post-Ugi-azide reaction

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Abstract

Ugi-azide four-component reaction (UA-4CR) as development on Ugi four-component reaction (U-4CR) is the condensation reaction involving an aldehyde, an amine, an isocyanide, and an azide source. Nowadays, UA-4CR has been employed for the efficient and facile production of 1,5-disubstituted-1H-tetrazoles (1,5-DS-1H-Ts). Interestingly, the combination of 1,5-DS-1H-Ts with suitable post-transformations in a tandem manner results in the construction of various classes of heterocyclic compounds bearing 1,5-DS-1H-T moiety. This review aims to provide the application of diverse post-Ugi-azide reaction in the preparation of different N-heterocyclic compounds bearing 1,5-DS-1H-T such as substituted and fused 1,5-DS-1H-Ts.

Keywords: 1,5-Disubstituted-1H-tetrazoles, 1,5-DS-1H-Ts, Isocyanides, MCRs, Multicomponent reaction, Post-Ugi-azide reaction, heterocyclic compound, tetrazole derivative, acylation, amidation, chemical analysis, chemical reaction